

THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AND ITS IMPACT ON POLITICAL CLEAVAGES IN EUROPE:

LESSONS LEARNED AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR DEMOCRATIC RESILIENCE

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REGROUP

REBUILDING GOVERNANCE AND
RESILIENCE OUT OF THE PANDEMIC

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Culminating more than a decade of crisis in Europe, the Covid-19 pandemic has opened an important window of opportunity for institutional and policy change, not only at the “reactive” level of emergency responses, but also to tackle more broadly the many socio-political challenges caused or exacerbated by Covid-19. Building on this premise, the Horizon Europe project REGROUP (*Rebuilding governance and resilience out of the pandemic*) aims to: 1) provide the European Union with a body of actionable advice on how to rebuild post-pandemic governance and public policies in an effective and democratic way; anchored to 2) a map of the socio-political dynamics and consequences of Covid-19; and 3) an empirically-informed normative evaluation of the pandemic.

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Executive summary

The Covid-19 pandemic has profoundly impacted European political landscapes, not by creating entirely new cleavages but by activating, intensifying, and reconfiguring existing political divisions. This policy paper examines how the pandemic affected political cleavages across the European Union. The analysis reveals the emergence of a health-economy trade-off dimension, the differential activation of economic versus cultural grievances, and the strategic role of populist radical right parties (PRRPs) in politicizing the crisis. Key findings indicate that while the pandemic created new arenas of contestation, traditional ideological orientations and trust in scientific institutions remained the strongest predictors of political attitudes and behaviors. The paper concludes with a set of policy recommendations for managing future crises while maintaining democratic resilience and social cohesion, that can be summarized as follows:

- **Build long-term trust in scientific institutions:** Invest in science communication, transparency protocols, and frameworks for communicating uncertainty to maintain public confidence.
- **Address legitimacy deficits of technocratic governance:** Ensure emergency measures are accompanied by robust democratic deliberation and parliamentary oversight to prevent populist exploitation of “corona dictatorship” narratives.
- **Implement differentiated communication strategies:** Tailor messaging to address distinct concerns, recognizing that economic grievances require different responses than cultural anxieties about freedom.
- **Design sector-specific economic support programs:** Create targeted interventions based on sectors’ essentiality and physicality, with direct income support for high-contact workers and digitalization assistance for adaptable businesses.
- **Engage labor organizations proactively:** Include trade unions in crisis planning to channel grievances through institutional rather than contentious channels.
- **Account for regional economic and political variations:** Tailor crisis policies to regional vulnerabilities and allow flexibility within coordinated European frameworks to prevent uneven protest responses across member states.
- **Maintain proportionality in emergency measures:** Implement sunset clauses and clear metrics for lifting restrictions to prevent the perception of disproportionate government overreach.

- **Preserve channels for democratic contestation:** Allow socially-distanced protests and maintain legitimate opposition spaces even during emergencies to prevent radicalization and integration with anti-system movements.
- **Strengthen democratic resilience through civic education:** Invest in media literacy and create participatory mechanisms that include societal representatives alongside scientific experts.

Keywords: political cleavages; health-economy tradeoff; populist parties; trust in science; pandemic protests; democratic resilience.

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic represented an unprecedented challenge to European democracies, forcing governments to implement extraordinary measures that restricted individual freedoms, curtailed economic activity, and fundamentally altered social interactions (Engler et al., 2021; Hale et al., 2021). Beyond its immediate health and economic impacts, the pandemic served as a critical juncture that revealed and reshaped underlying political tensions within European societies (Ferrera et al., 2023; Kriesi & Oana, 2023). This policy paper examines how the pandemic affected political cleavages across the European Union, drawing on extensive empirical research to understand the dynamics of politicization, mobilization and protest during this extraordinary period.

The analysis presented here synthesizes findings from the three research papers produced by Work Package 3 (“Old and New Cleavages in Pandemic Times”) of project REGROUP, while also drawing on a comprehensive review of the broader scholarly literature on Covid-19’s political impact across Europe.

The first paper (Caramani et al., 2023) examines the emergence of a health-economy trade-off dimension through analysis of survey data from multiple European countries, revealing how sectoral affectedness shaped policy preferences across different occupational groups. This study demonstrates that while workers in sectors characterized by high physicality and low essentiality (such as hospitality and entertainment) faced severe economic disruption, their policy preferences did not significantly differ from unaffected respondents, suggesting that ideological orientations and trust in scientific institutions were more powerful predictors than material circumstances.

The second paper (Volk et al., 2023) focuses on the role of populist radical right parties as cleavage agents during the pandemic, analyzing their strategic framing of Covid-19 restrictions across different national contexts. Through detailed discourse analysis of parties like Germany’s AfD, the Netherlands’ Forum for Democracy, and Poland’s Law and Justice party, the research traces their evolution from initial support for lockdowns to embracing elaborate conspiracy theories and “corona dictatorship” narratives, demonstrating how these parties successfully consolidated a transnational cultural super-cleavage.

The third paper (Moutselos, 2025) provides a comprehensive analysis of pandemic-related protests across the EU-27 using data from the Armed Conflict Location & Event Data (ACLED), documenting the differential mobilization of economic versus cultural grievances, with Southern European countries experiencing higher volumes of economically-motivated protests organized by traditional left-wing actors, while Northern European countries saw more culturally-oriented mobilization around issues of freedom and vaccination mandates. This research also reveals the temporal dynamics of protest,

showing how economic grievances mobilized quickly in early 2020 while cultural protests peaked during the vaccination mandate period of late 2021 and early 2022.

Together, these studies employ diverse methodological approaches - including large-scale survey analysis, protest event data coding, political discourse analysis, social media content examination, and comparative case studies - to offer a nuanced understanding of how the pandemic interacted with pre-existing political divisions and created new forms of contestation. While these three papers form the empirical core of this policy brief, the analysis is enriched by insights from the extensive scholarly literature on pandemic politics that has emerged since 2020, with researchers across Europe examining Covid-19's political impact through various theoretical and empirical lenses (see, among many others: Kriesi & Oana, 2023; della Porta, 2024; Hellmeier, 2023; Bobba & Hubé, 2021; Engler et al., 2021; Rovny et al., 2022; Burciu & Hutter, 2023).

Understanding these dynamics is crucial for policymakers seeking to navigate future crises while maintaining democratic legitimacy and social cohesion. The pandemic revealed both the resilience and vulnerabilities of European political systems, offering important lessons for crisis management, political communication, and democratic governance (Ferrera et al., 2023). This paper provides a comprehensive analysis of these dynamics and concludes with evidence-based policy recommendations for strengthening European democracies' capacity to manage future health crises.

This policy paper is organized as follows. Section 2 establishes the theoretical framework for understanding political cleavages in times of crisis, examining how traditional European cleavages have evolved and how crises serve as catalysts for political change. Section 3 analyzes the emergence of the health-economy divide as a new dimension of political conflict, exploring how sectoral impacts shaped political preferences and why ideological factors proved more influential than material circumstances. Section 4 examines the activation of cultural cleavages, focusing on the politicization of science and freedom and the strategic role of populist parties in framing the pandemic as a "corona dictatorship." Section 5 documents the geographic and temporal variations in pandemic politics, revealing distinct regional patterns of mobilization and the absence of a sustained rallying effect. Section 6 discusses the consolidation of a cultural super-cleavage and its implications for party competition and democratic politics. Section 7 analyzes protest repertoires and mobilization strategies, including innovations in collective action and patterns of transnational diffusion. Section 8 explores the limits of cross-cutting mobilization, examining why economic and cultural grievances remained largely separate. Section 9 presents comprehensive policy recommendations in three key areas: crisis communication and trust building, managing economic disruption, and protecting democratic spaces. The paper concludes with reflections on the pandemic's lasting impact on European democracy and the lessons for future crisis management.

Theoretical framework: understanding political cleavages in times of crisis

To understand how the Covid-19 pandemic affected European politics, we must first examine the evolution of political cleavages that have shaped democratic competition in Europe. Political cleavages - the deep, structural divisions that organize political conflict - have long shaped European party systems and democratic politics. The traditional cleavages identified by Lipset and Rokkan (1967), including class, religion, and center-periphery divisions, have undergone significant transformation in recent decades (Ignazi, 1992; Kitschelt, 1994, 1995). The erosion of these traditional divisions has been accompanied by the emergence of new conflicts, particularly along cultural and value-based dimensions (Kriesi et al., 2008; Norris & Inglehart, 2019).

The Covid-19 pandemic occurred within this context of evolving cleavage structures. As the erosion and restructuring process of societal cleavages thus helped newcomer parties to capture politico-cultural opportunities by focusing on new issues - and by politicizing and mobilizing voters along new lines of conflict (Hooghe et al., 2018; Ford & Jennings, 2020). The pandemic provided a unique opportunity to observe how extraordinary circumstances interact with existing political divisions and potentially create new ones (Rovny et al., 2022).

This interaction between crisis and political change deserves particular attention. Crises often serve as critical junctures that can accelerate political change and realign existing cleavages (Capoccia & Kelemen, 2011; Seabrooke & Tsingou, 2019). The Covid-19 pandemic represented a life-and-death issue, creating conditions for potential political transformation. However, the relationship between crisis and political change is complex and mediated by numerous factors, including institutional structures, political agency, and pre-existing political cultures (Moffitt, 2015).

The pandemic's unique characteristics - its global scope, prolonged duration, and comprehensive impact on all aspects of social life - created distinctive conditions for political mobilization. Populist radical right parties (henceforth, PRRPs) thus often act as the mediators and performers of crises, aiming to discredit the elected political establishment and further their own electoral gain (Ringe & Rennó, 2023). This performative dimension of crisis politics proved particularly important during the pandemic, as different political actors competed to frame the crisis and its appropriate responses.

Finally, understanding how the pandemic affected political cleavages requires attention to both the "demand side" (citizens' grievances and preferences) and the "supply side" (political actors' strategies and framing). While structural conditions created by the pandemic (economic disruption, health threats, restrictions on freedom) generated

potential for political mobilization, the actual patterns of contestation were shaped by how political actors - particularly political parties and social movements - interpreted and politicized these conditions (della Porta, 2024). The interplay between structural grievances and political agency produced the distinctive patterns of pandemic politics observed across Europe.

The health-economy divide: a new dimension of conflict

Among the most significant political dynamics during the pandemic was the emergence of what scholars termed the “health-economy divide.” Covid-19 related policy preferences are conceptualized along a continuum between a “health” pole and an “economy” pole. On the “health” pole, one finds preferences for policies that prioritize the health of citizens and the sustainability of public and private health systems. On the “economy” pole, one finds preferences to keep the economy running, that is, ensure mobility, keep shops open, not restrict transportation, etc. (Oana et al., 2021; Caramani et al., 2023).

This trade-off became a central organizing principle of pandemic politics, structuring debates about appropriate policy responses and generating new forms of political conflict. The health-economy dimension cut across traditional left-right divisions in complex ways, creating new coalitions and oppositions that did not map neatly onto existing political alignments (Carrieri et al., 2021).

The pandemic’s differential impact on economic sectors proved crucial in shaping political responses and understanding this new dimension. Caramani et al. (2023) identified two key factors determining sectoral vulnerability: “Essentiality” is defined as a matter of survival at both individual and systemic level. For example, care workers are essential for certain individuals, while power grid workers are essential for the social system to work. The same applies for sectors that do not rely on physical contact. “Physicality” is defined as the degree to which an activity is constrained by space and contact or, on the contrary, can transcend location. This sectoral differentiation had important political, and substantive, consequences. The results clearly suggest that belonging to any of the three categories theorized as more affected by the Covid-19 mitigation measures raises the probability of unemployment, reduced income or working hours, and/or forced leave or furlough vis-à-vis the least affected category (essential, non-physical).

Workers in highly affected sectors - such as hospitality, entertainment, and personal services - faced severe economic disruption, potentially creating new political grievances and alignments (Müller et al., 2022).

However, the relationship between sectoral impact and political preferences proved more complex than initially hypothesized. One result that immediately stands out is that those who were negatively affected by the pandemic do not significantly differ in their policy preferences from the respondents who did not declare any adverse consequences (Caramani et al., 2023). This surprising finding suggests that ideological and partisan factors mediated the translation of economic grievances into political preferences, as argued also by other scholars (Slothuus & Bisgaard, 2021; Rovny et al., 2022).

This limited impact of economic affectedness on policy preferences points to the importance of non-material factors in pandemic politics, challenging conventional assumptions about economic determinism. Two of the most significant predictors of individuals' policy preferences for dealing with the pandemic are attitudinal: ideological orientation and trust in scientists (see also Brouard et al., 2020; Kritzinger et al., 2021). This finding challenges purely structural or economic explanations of pandemic politics and highlights the continued relevance of ideological and cultural factors.

Trust in scientific institutions emerged as a particularly important factor. Citizens with higher trust in scientists were more likely to support health-prioritizing policies, while those with lower trust were more skeptical of restrictions and mandates (Caramani et al., 2023; Jennings et al., 2021). This pattern reflects broader tensions around expertise and authority that have characterized contemporary politics, with the pandemic intensifying existing debates about the role of scientific knowledge in policymaking (Bertsou & Caramani, 2022).

The activation of cultural cleavages

Beyond economic concerns, the pandemic activated deep cultural divisions within European societies, particularly around science and freedom. These cultural conflicts centered on fundamental questions about the balance between collective health and individual freedom, the authority of scientific expertise, and the legitimacy of state intervention in personal choices. Moutselos (2025) shows that the majority of protests categorized as culture-related among the EU-27 were centred around vaccination mandates and associated restrictions and somewhat less around the initial lockdowns, echoing the findings of Neumayer et al. (2024).

The cultural dimension of pandemic politics manifested in various forms of science skepticism and conspiracy theories. Cultural grievances were often fuelled by conspiracy theories, such as the rumour (widespread in a surprising number of EU countries early on) that the introduction of 5G networks was somehow associated with the virus, a conspiracy that led, for instance in the Netherlands, to extensive destruction of 5G

towers; QAnon conspiracies; or the view (mostly in Eastern Europe) that Bill Gates and George Soros held responsibility for the crisis (Grande et al., 2021; Hunger et al., 2023).

Populist radical right parties played a crucial role in activating and amplifying these cultural grievances through their mobilization of the “corona dictatorship” frame. AfD soon framed the preventive measures as such as an “unlawful attack of the government against the people”, while fashioning itself as a “defender of freedom” (Rensmann & de Zee, 2022). This framing strategy positioned pandemic restrictions as part of a broader assault on democratic freedoms by allegedly authoritarian elites. The concept of “corona dictatorship” became a powerful mobilizing frame across multiple European countries. AfD politicians took advantage of the virtual space to deplore the supposed “corona dictatorship” instituted by the federal government (Volk & Weisskircher, 2024). This frame effectively connected pandemic restrictions to broader populist narratives about elite oppression and the betrayal of “the people” (Volk et al., 2023).

Different populist parties adapted this basic frame to their specific national contexts. In Germany, the AfD’s political discourse portrayed the pandemic as a continuation of allegedly anti-democratic and anti-constitutional politics by the government, linking it to previous crises including the 2008 European financial crisis and the 2015 migration crisis (Rensmann & de Zee, 2022; Volk & Weisskircher, 2024). This narrative strategy positioned the pandemic as the latest in a series of crises exploited by elites to expand their power at the expense of popular sovereignty.

The political narratives around the pandemic evolved significantly over time, particularly among populist actors. In the Netherlands, for example, at the onset of the pandemic, FvD was actually one of the few parties in the Netherlands (alongside the PVV) that pushed for stricter lockdown measures (de Lange, 2023). However, this position quickly shifted: by April 2020, pleas for stricter lockdown measures started to give way for calls to transition out of the lockdown (Crum, 2023). This evolution culminated in the embrace of elaborate conspiracy theories. It was not until January 2021 (which also marked the official start of the electoral campaign for the 2021 election) that the party started to criticize the lockdown measures by openly and wholeheartedly embracing conspiracy myths (de Jonge, 2021). The adoption of the “Great Reset” narrative exemplified this shift, with populist actors claiming that global elites were using the pandemic to implement a pre-planned transformation of society.

The strategies employed by populist parties varied significantly depending on whether they were in government or opposition. Studies have found that PRRPs in opposition initially used the pandemic to attack government (Rovira Kaltwasser & Taggart 2022), and then attempted to align it with their nativist agenda (Wondreys & Mudde 2022), while populist parties in power seemed to engage in denial before shifting to ‘blame-avoidance’ and ‘blame-shifting’ (Bobba & Hubé, 2021; Volpi et al. 2022).

In Poland, where the populist Law and Justice party (PiS) was in power, the pandemic response was shaped by electoral considerations. PiS did not proclaim the ‘state of emergency’ or ‘state of natural disaster’ but merely mandated restrictions to social life (‘lockdown’) since, according to the Polish constitution, the state of emergency would have considerably delayed the presidential elections (Lipiński, 2021; Vashchan-ka, 2020). The party’s discourse combined pandemic management with traditional cul- tural themes: the aim of PiS to protect Polish families from Covid-19 was occasionally articulated together with homophobic discourse defining LGBT as an ‘ideology’ that was “worse than communism” (Lipiński, 2021; Styczyńska & Zubek, 2023).

Geographical and temporal variations in pan- demic politics

The pandemic’s political impact varied significantly across European regions, reflect- ing different political cultures, institutional structures, and pre-existing patterns of contention. According to the abovementioned analysis based on ACLED data, Moutselos (2025) claims that Southern European countries experienced, on average, higher vol- umes of Covid-related protest events, while Central-Eastern European countries saw lower volumes (Hellmeier, 2023). These regional differences reflected deeper variations in political culture and protest traditions. This striking finding seems to confirm the ag- onistic protest culture in Southern Europe (which interacts, to some extent, with parti- san orientation of the protesters, with left-wing actors being more present in Southern European countries), which may reflect less consensual political cultures, the historical legacies of democratic transition, or a reaction to an otherwise closed political oppor- tunity structure (Andronikidou & Kovras, 2012; Malamidis, 2020).

The content and framing of protests also varied regionally. The northern countries of Austria, Germany, and Denmark experienced consistently higher percentages of cul- ture-based mobilization at the beginning of the pandemic, while Southern countries, in- cluding Italy, Portugal, and Spain (but also the northern countries France and Belgium), saw protests revolving consistently around economic issues and organized often at a national stage by mainstream left-wing actors, such as trade unions (see also Thomas et al., 2024).

These regional patterns evolved over time, revealing important dynamics about crisis mobilization and the limits of government legitimacy. Contrary to expectations of a sustained “rally around the flag” effect, Moutselos (2025) does not find evidence for an overall “rallying effect” in the EU-27 space, as protests were already recorded in April- May 2020 following the imposition of the first lockdowns and remained reliably high for the non-summer months (Schraff, 2021; van der Meer et al., 2023). The absence of

a general rallying effect masked important variations by type of grievance. If one can infer the existence of a “rallying effect”, this may have been limited to culture-related protests - as economy actors protested in large numbers already in April 2020. This pattern suggests that economic grievances mobilized more quickly than cultural ones, with the latter gaining prominence only as the pandemic wore on and vaccination policies were implemented (Jørgensen et al., 2022).

The peak of mobilization occurred in late 2021 and early 2022, coinciding with the introduction of vaccination mandates and Covid passes. Mobilization peaked in the winter months of 2021-2022, when Covid passes and the associated vaccination mandates became heavily contested in a number of countries (Plümper et al., 2021). This timing reflects the cumulative effect of pandemic fatigue and the particularly contentious nature of vaccination requirements.

While regional patterns were important, national specificities often proved decisive in shaping pandemic politics. These specificities reflected what scholars term “politi-co-cultural opportunity structures”, namely nationally specific formations of value conflict (e.g. the persistent role of a politicized Catholicism-secularism divide in Poland as a driver of political conflict); distinct societal perceptions of political conflicts; particular cultural discourses and the changing ‘boundaries of the speakable’ in public discourse, as well as the social/historical meaning of (idealized) national narratives about national identity and the past (Couperus et al., 2023).

In Germany, for example, the group Querdenken (“Lateral Thinking”) emerged as a distinctive form of pandemic protest that combined diverse ideological elements. This group organized protests on the cultural dimension across Germany, casting doubt on the necessity of protective measures, defending fundamental freedoms, and criticizing press coverage of the pandemic (Grande, 2023). The movement’s ability to bridge different political traditions while maintaining a focus on individual freedom reflected specifically German political dynamics and historical sensitivities.

In Central and Eastern European countries, pandemic protests often incorporated pre-existing political conflicts. In Slovenia, for instance, ongoing pro-democracy (and anti-corruption) protests incorporated grievances against the handling of the pandemic in the first half of 2020 with ease, leading to the country’s largest sustained demonstrations during this period (Borbáth et al., 2021). Similar patterns emerged in the Czech Republic and Poland, where pro-democracy movements seamlessly integrated pandemic grievances into broader critiques of government legitimacy (Rak, 2021; Turska-Kawa et al., 2022).

The consolidation of a cultural super-cleavage

The pandemic's political effects can best be understood not as creating entirely new cleavages but as accelerating and consolidating existing trends toward a comprehensive cultural divide in European politics. This raises important theoretical questions about the nature of contemporary political divisions. Whether this constitutes a fully-fledged cleavage in the classical sense - with deep social roots and organizational manifestation - or represents a more fluid dimension of political competition remains an open theoretical question. What is clear is that this new politico-cultural super cleavage sets value orientations towards liberal-pluralist inclusiveness against authoritarian-populist (nostalgic) nationalism. It subsumes a whole range of issues that instantaneously become part of a cultural divide, combining (anti-)feminism and (trans-)gender politics, climate change and climate change skepticism, migration and anti-migration, and pandemic public health policies as well (Volk et al. 2023).

This super-cleavage represents more than a simple aggregation of issue positions. Rather, as Volk et al. (2023) suggest, it reflects a fundamental divide about the nature of society, authority, and knowledge. On one side stands a worldview emphasizing scientific expertise, cosmopolitan values, and collective responsibility; on the other, a perspective prioritizing traditional authority, national sovereignty, and individual freedom from state interference (see also Inglehart & Norris, 2019).

Populist radical right parties played a crucial role in consolidating this cultural super-cleavage through their pandemic responses. PRRPs tended to frame, often successfully, the politico-cultural super cleavage, and thereby all societal conflicts, in terms of an anti-pluralist notion of an antagonism between alleged “totalitarian elites” and the (values of the) “democratic people” (Mudde & Rovira Kaltwasser, 2018).

This framing strategy proved particularly effective because it could incorporate diverse grievances under a single narrative umbrella. Whether the specific issue was mask mandates, vaccination requirements, or economic restrictions, populist actors consistently framed these as manifestations of elite oppression against popular will. These parties contributed to the creation and consolidation of a newly emerged, transnational politico-cultural super cleavage, which, in turn, is fueling broader shifts in European party systems (Zulianello & Guasti, 2023).

The consolidation of the cultural super-cleavage has profound implications for party competition and democratic politics. Traditional left-right divisions based on economic redistribution have not disappeared but have been overlaid and often overshadowed by cultural conflicts (Häusermann & Kriesi, 2015). This creates new challenges for mainstream parties, which must navigate between their traditional constituencies and new cultural divisions.

The pandemic accelerated this process by forcing all political actors to take clear positions on issues that, while not entirely new, suddenly became urgent and unavoidable, and mapped directly onto the cultural dimension: the authority of scientific expertise, the legitimacy of state restrictions on individual behavior, and the balance between collective and individual responsibility. These positions often cut across traditional party lines, creating internal tensions and new opportunities for political realignment (Marks et al., 2021).

Protest repertoires and mobilization strategies

The pandemic created unique conditions for political protest, with traditional forms of collective action restricted by the very policies being contested. This paradox led to both the adaptation of existing repertoires and the development of new forms of contention. Innovation in the form of remoulding older repertoires into pandemic-specific ones took place: car rides, trucker convoys, and tractor demonstrations were mostly used in economy-related protest (Pressman & Choi-Fitzpatrick, 2021). Instead, traditional protest forms persisted but were often modified to accommodate or deliberately violate pandemic restrictions; in many cases, ignoring requirements to wear masks or keep distance became themselves acts of disobedience. This transformation of public health measures into sites of political contestation exemplified how the pandemic politicized everyday behaviors (Rohlinger & Meyer, 2024).

Moreover, several protests creatively adapted to restrictions while maintaining their contentious character. In Spain, the well-known banging-pots demonstration was very popular amidst lockdowns, especially since it was a form of protest that could be employed in isolation on a balcony (della Porta & Lavizzari, 2024). Such adaptations demonstrated protesters' ability to maintain collective action even under severe constraints.

Despite the primarily national focus of pandemic policies and protests, significant transnational diffusion of protest frames and tactics occurred, alongside patterns of counter-mobilization. In late 2021 and 2022, a number of large demonstrations assumed transnational characteristics, and mobilization frames became global - often with the aid of social media. Truck drivers from Poland, Italy, and Germany drove their trucks to Brussels to protest "for freedom", with references to the Canadian Freedom Convoy (Fominaya, 2024). The "freedom convoy" model exemplified successful transnational diffusion, appearing in various forms across European countries. Similarly, another repertoire that was retransformed in the context of the pandemic and assumed transnational characteristics was that of the "yellow vests" (Fillieule & Dafflon, 2013). Aside from France, they appeared in protests in Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Greece, and the Netherlands.

However, despite these transnational elements, protests regarding Covid-19 remained largely national affairs. Despite the European Commission's role in coordinating with national governments on the Recovery and Resilience Facility and the implementation of Covid passes, protesters did not communicate grievances towards the EU but towards their national and sometimes regional governments (Capati et al., 2022). This national focus reflects both the primarily national character of pandemic governance and the continued salience of national political spaces for contentious politics (della Porta & Caiani, 2007).

The pandemic also witnessed significant counter-mobilization, particularly in countries with strong anti-fascist traditions. One notable pattern (particularly in Austria, Germany, Ireland, and Greece) was the organization of counter-demonstrations. These often took the form of organized events against Covid-19 measures by the far right and were accompanied by left-wing counter-demonstrations, such as those held by anti-fascist groups. Germany exemplified this dynamic of mobilization and counter-mobilization. The peculiar street-level Kulturkampf around the pandemic is illustrated by the fact that Germany was the only country among the EU-27 where medical students systematically organized protests to defend the vaccination campaigns. More generally, Germany recorded the most recorded counter-demonstrations by a wide margin, often pitting left-wing against right-wing groups and reflecting patterns of protest and counter-protest long present in that country (Volk, 2023).

The limits of cross-cutting mobilization

While both economic and cultural grievances were activated during the pandemic, successful mobilization across these dimensions proved remarkably difficult. During the Covid-19 crisis, the simultaneous activation of economic and cultural concerns by the same group, organization, or movement was observed infrequently. Actors usually mobilized on one or the other dimension, and economic protesters kept their efforts separate from coronavirus deniers and vaccine sceptics (Borbáth, 2024).

The few attempts to bridge these dimensions revealed the challenges involved. The French CGT trade union exemplified these difficulties. Initially focused on economic grievances and worker protection, the union gradually incorporated cultural themes about freedom and coercion; by late 2021, they had even begun using language typically recorded in right-wing, culture-oriented protests (Moutselos, 2025).

Student movements provided another illuminating case of attempts to bridge different grievance dimensions. Students were actually one of the most active protest actors in this period, especially in Southern Europe, but this population has remained relatively

underexplored in the literature on Covid protests (Hunt, 2022). Their protests revealed the tensions involved in maintaining coalitions across different types of grievances. Greek student movements particularly struggled with internal divisions. They sometimes lamented distance learning and poor school conditions, and in other cases, they castigated police repression and vaccination mandates. This led to within-group tensions, for instance among the highly active Greek high-school students: some were in favour of further measures and protocols, while others were vehemently against police intervention and further restrictions such as mask wearing (Moutselos 2025).

The challenge for these movements was maintaining coherent frames while appealing to diverse constituencies. All such groups had to confront the lack of a coherent critique of technocratic/scientific knowledge. Without this critique, simultaneous calls for respecting individual liberties, controlling repression, and providing more resources to schools, universities, and professional sectors were superseded by the priority of public health as the most important public good for the “people” (Coen et al., 2022).

Policy implications and recommendations

A number of policy recommendations can be derived from the analysis presented in the previous paragraphs, which fall into three main areas: crisis communication and trust building, managing economic disruption, and protecting democratic spaces during emergencies. To prepare for potential future pandemics, policymakers - at both national and EU level - should prioritize interventions in these critical domains.

Firstly, the three main research papers demonstrate that trust in scientific institutions and governments provides the foundation for social cohesion during health emergencies. The pandemic revealed significant vulnerabilities in how governments communicate uncertainty and maintain legitimacy during crises. Three key recommendations emerge from the pandemic experience:

Building long-term trust in scientific institutions: Trust in scientists was one of the strongest predictors of support for public health measures during the pandemic (Bertsou & Caramani, 2022). To prepare for future crises, governments should invest early in science communication and institutional transparency. This includes sustained support for independent scientific bodies, promoting scientific literacy among the public, and—crucially—developing clear protocols for communicating scientific uncertainty. The absence of such frameworks in some countries led to confusion and mistrust, as virologists presented evolving knowledge as definitive truth on mass media. A more effective approach is to explicitly communicate what is known, what remains uncertain, and why rules may change in the future. Such transparency helps manage expectations and

maintains credibility over time: for instance, during the early stages of the pandemic, the Netherlands' approach of explicitly stating what was known and what wasn't helped reduce backlash when guidelines evolved.

Addressing the legitimacy deficit: The finding that centrist, grand coalition, and technocratic governments were more likely to experience protests than partisan governments suggests that technocratic approaches to crisis management may face particular legitimacy challenges (Caramani, 2017). For instance, in France, President Macron's centralised and expert-driven response was often viewed as top-down, sparking resistance and offshoots of the *Gilets Jaunes* focused on vaccine mandates; in contrast, countries like Portugal - where the socialist government combined expert advice with visible parliamentary oversight - faced fewer street-level protests and enjoyed relatively higher compliance. Policymakers should learn from these experiences and ensure that emergency measures are accompanied by robust democratic deliberation and clear accountability mechanisms.

Differentiated communication strategies: The activation of different grievances by different political groups suggests the need for targeted communication strategies. Economic concerns require different responses than cultural anxieties about freedom and authority. One-size-fits-all messaging may fail to address the specific concerns of different constituencies (Crabu et al., 2021).

Secondly, the rapid emergence of economic protests at the pandemic's outset, when the unavoidable lockdowns paralyzed European economies, demonstrates the importance of swift and comprehensive economic support measures. In this regard policy recommendations - not all derived from the three research papers on which this brief is based - include:

Sector-specific support programs: Given the differential impact on sectors based on their essentiality and physicality, support programs should be tailored to sectoral needs. Sectors with high physicality and low essentiality require different interventions than those able to adapt to remote operations (Caramani et al., 2023). For example, hospitality and entertainment workers need direct income support and retraining opportunities, while retail businesses require rent relief and digitalization assistance. Germany's *Kurzarbeit* scheme and France's partial unemployment benefits demonstrated how sector-specific approaches can prevent mass layoffs, while the Netherlands' *TOZO* scheme specifically targeted self-employed workers in affected sectors (Müller et al., 2022).

Proactive engagement with labor organizations: The prominent role of trade unions in organizing economic protests suggests the importance of including labor representatives in crisis planning and response. Early engagement may help channel grievances through institutional rather than contentious channels (Thomas et al., 2024). Austria's social

partnership model, where unions participated directly in designing pandemic support measures, resulted in fewer protests than countries where labor was excluded from decision-making. Similarly, Denmark's tripartite negotiations between government, employers, and unions produced rapid agreement on wage compensation schemes that maintained social peace (Borbáth et al., 2021).

Addressing regional variations: The higher protest levels in Southern Europe point to the need for policies that account for regional economic vulnerabilities and political cultures. European-level coordination should allow for national and regional adaptation (Salvati, 2021). The EU's Recovery and Resilience Facility recognized this by allowing member states to design their own recovery plans, even though variation among national plans in the end was quite low (Caramani and Cicchi 2024); Spain's regional approach permitted Catalonia and the Basque Country to implement distinct support measures reflecting their economic structures; Italy's differentiated regional lockdown system, though controversial, attempted to balance local economic needs with health requirements, demonstrating the importance of flexibility in crisis response (Truchlewski et al., 2021).

Thirdly and finally, the pandemic exposed a fundamental tension between the need for rapid, decisive action to protect public health and the imperative to maintain democratic accountability and legitimacy. Future crisis preparedness must therefore extend beyond health and economic considerations to encompass the preservation of democratic norms and practices. Three key recommendations emerge from the pandemic experience:

Maintaining proportionality: Emergency measures should be clearly time-limited and proportionate to the threat. The framing of restrictions as "corona dictatorship" by populist actors gained traction partly because some measures appeared to lack clear endpoints or proportionality principles (Truchlewski et al., 2021). Sweden's approach, while controversial, maintained public trust by avoiding blanket lockdowns and relying on recommendations rather than mandates. In contrast, the Netherlands' curfew measures faced legal challenges and sparked riots partly because they were perceived as disproportionate to the threat. Best practices include sunset clauses (as used in Denmark's emergency legislation), regular parliamentary review (Germany's Bundestag voted monthly on extending measures), and clear metrics for lifting restrictions (Norway's traffic light system linking measures to infection rates).

Preserving channels for democratic contestation: Even during emergencies, democratic societies need channels for legitimate opposition and contestation. The suppression of protest or the closing of democratic spaces may paradoxically increase radicalization and undermine legitimacy (Louwerse et al., 2021). The Netherlands' allowance of socially-distanced protests prevented the escalation seen in countries with blanket

protest bans. Germany's Constitutional Court ruling that protests could continue with safety measures demonstrated how democratic rights can be preserved during health emergencies. Conversely, strict protest bans in countries like Slovenia coincided with the integration of pandemic grievances into broader anti-government movements, suggesting that providing legitimate outlets for dissent is crucial for maintaining social stability.

Strengthening democratic resilience: The success of populist actors in framing the pandemic in anti-pluralist terms highlights the need for long-term investments in democratic education and institutions. This includes supporting independent media, civil society organizations, and democratic participation mechanisms (Crum & Oleart, 2023). Finland's high trust in institutions and low susceptibility to conspiracy theories reflected decades of investment in media literacy education. Ireland's Citizens' Assembly model could be adapted for pandemic decision-making, bringing citizen voices into policy discussions. France's citizen consultation on vaccine strategy, though imperfect, demonstrated how participatory mechanisms can enhance legitimacy. Countries should also strengthen fact-checking initiatives, support local journalism, and create permanent advisory bodies that include diverse societal representatives alongside scientific experts.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 pandemic served as an extraordinary stress test for European democracies, revealing both their capacity for adaptation and their underlying vulnerabilities. This policy brief has examined how the pandemic interacted with and transformed political cleavages across the European Union, drawing on comprehensive empirical research to understand the complex dynamics of political mobilization, protest, and the asymmetric impact of this unprecedented crisis.

Our analysis yields several key findings with important implications for future crisis management. First, rather than creating entirely new political divisions, the pandemic primarily activated and intensified existing cleavages, particularly along cultural lines. While the health-economy trade-off emerged as a novel dimension of political conflict, it was rapidly absorbed into broader cultural divisions between liberal-pluralist and authoritarian-populist worldviews. This suggests that future crises - whether health-related, environmental, or geopolitical - will likely be interpreted through similar cultural lenses, requiring policymakers to anticipate and address not just material concerns but also symbolic and values-based anxieties.

Second, the research demonstrates that ideological orientations and trust in scientific institutions proved more powerful than material circumstances in shaping political preferences during the pandemic (Caramani et al., 2023). Workers in severely affected sectors did not automatically translate their economic hardship into support for economy-prioritizing policies; instead, their responses were mediated by pre-existing political beliefs and institutional trust. This finding underscores the critical importance of building and maintaining public trust in democratic and scientific institutions during non-crisis periods as an investment in future crisis resilience.

Third, the strategic role of populist radical right parties in consolidating a transnational cultural super-cleavage reveals how political entrepreneurs can successfully exploit crises to advance their agendas (Volk et al., 2023). By framing pandemic restrictions as manifestations of elite oppression and weaving together diverse grievances - from vaccine skepticism to economic anxieties - these parties demonstrated the performative dimension of crisis politics. Their evolution from initially supporting strict measures to embracing conspiracy theories and “corona dictatorship” narratives highlights the dynamic and opportunistic nature of populist mobilization.

Fourth, the geographic and temporal variations in pandemic politics - from the prevalence of economic protests in Southern Europe to cultural mobilization in Northern countries, from the rapid emergence of economic grievances to the later surge in anti-vaccination protests - demonstrate that crisis responses are deeply embedded in national contexts and path dependencies (Moutselos 2025). One-size-fits-all approaches to crisis management are therefore likely to fail; successful strategies must account for regional variations, political cultures, and institutional legacies.

The pandemic also revealed significant limitations in cross-cutting political mobilization. Despite the simultaneous activation of economic and cultural grievances, actors rarely succeeded in bridging these dimensions, with traditional left-wing organizations focusing on material concerns while right-wing movements emphasized freedom and anti-system narratives. This fragmentation suggests that the cultural super-cleavage may be becoming increasingly difficult to transcend, posing challenges for democratic politics that require broad coalitions to address complex, multifaceted crises.

Looking ahead, European democracies face the dual challenge of preparing for future crises while healing the divisions exposed and deepened by the pandemic. The policy recommendations outlined in this brief - from building long-term trust in scientific institutions to preserving democratic spaces during emergencies - offer parsimonious, evidence-based strategies for enhancing crisis resilience. However, their implementation requires sustained political will and recognition that crisis preparedness extends beyond technical measures to encompass the fundamental legitimacy of democratic governance.

As Europe has emerged from the pandemic and confronts new challenges - from climate change to geopolitical instability following Russia's invasion of Ukraine - the lessons learned from Covid-19 remain profoundly relevant. The pandemic demonstrated that effective crisis management requires not just epidemiological expertise or economic resources, but also careful attention to political dynamics, cultural sensitivities, and democratic values. Success in future crises will depend on the ability of European democracies to maintain public trust, ensure inclusive decision-making, and prevent the further disruption by populist and radical parties that undermines collective problem-solving capacity.

One may rightfully claim that the Covid-19 pandemic has faded from immediate concern, but its political legacy will endure. It has accelerated the transformation of European party systems, consolidated new patterns of political conflict, and revealed both the resilience and fragility of democratic institutions. By understanding these dynamics and implementing appropriate reforms, European democracies can emerge stronger and better prepared for the inevitable crises that lie ahead.

Bibliography

- Altiparmakis, A., Bojar, A., Brouard, S., Foucault, M., Kriesi, H., & Nadeau, R. (2021). Pandemic politics: Policy evaluations of government responses to COVID-19. *West European Politics*, 44(5-6), 1159-1179.
- Andronikidou, A., & Kovras, I. (2012). Cultures of rioting and anti-systemic politics in Southern Europe. *West European Politics*, 35(4), 707-725.
- Belchior, A. M. (2024). Widening the gap of political inequality? The effect of the COVID-19 pandemic on political engagement. *European Political Science Review*, 16(4), 557-577.
- Bertsou, E., & Caramani, D. (2022). People haven't had enough of experts: Measuring technocratic attitudes among citizens in nine European countries. *American Journal of Political Science*, 66(2), 5-23.
- Bobba, G., & Hubé, N. (2021). *Populism and the politicization of the COVID-19 crisis in Europe*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Borbáth, E. (2024). Differentiation in protest politics: Participation by political insiders and outsiders. *Political Behavior*, 46(2), 727-750.
- Borbáth, E., Hunger, S., Hutter, S., & Oana, I. E. (2021). Civic and political engagement during the multifaceted COVID-19 crisis. *Swiss Political Science Review*, 27(2), 311-324.
- Bornschier, S. (2018). Globalization, cleavages, and the radical right. In J. Rydgren (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of the radical right* (pp. 212-238). New York: Oxford University Press.
- Brouard, S., Vasilopoulos, P., & Becher, M. (2020). Sociodemographic and psychological correlates of compliance with the COVID-19 public health measures in France. *Canadian Journal of Political Science/Revue Canadienne de Science Politique*, 53(2), 253-258.
- Burciu, R., & Hutter, S. (2023). More stress, less voice? The gender gap in political participation during the COVID-19 pandemic. *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 6(1), 114-133.
- Capati, A., Improta, M., & Trastulli, F. (2022). Covid-19 and party competition over the EU: Italy in early pandemic times. *European Politics and Society* (online first).
- Capoccia, G., & Kelemen, D. R. (2011). The study of critical junctures: Theory, narrative, and counterfactuals in historical institutionalism. *World Politics*, 59,

341-369.

- Caramani, D. (2017). Will vs. reason: The populist and technocratic forms of political representation and their critique to party government. *American Political Science Review*, 111(1), 54-67.
- Caramani, D., Cicchi, L., & Petrova, A. (2023). The health-economy divide: A structural analysis of sectoral affectedness and Covid-19 policy preferences in Europe. *REGROUP Research Paper 3*.
- Caramani, D., & Cicchi, L. (2024). The Relief-Reform Divide: An analysis of national responses to Covid-19 in seven EU Member States' recovery plans. *REGROUP Research Paper 10*.
- Carrieri, V., De Paola, M., & Gioia, F. (2021). The health-economy trade-off during the Covid-19 pandemic: Communication matters. *PLoS One*.
- Coen, S., Vezzoli, M., & Zogmaister, C. (2022). Theoretical and methodological approaches to activism during the COVID-19 pandemic—Between continuity and change. *Frontiers in Political Science*, 4, 844591.
- Couperus, S., Rensmann, L., & Tortola, P. D. (2023). Historical legacies and the political mobilization of national nostalgia: Understanding populism's relationship to the past. *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*, 31(2), 253-267.
- Crabu, S., Giardullo, P., Sciandra, A., & Neresini, F. (2021). Politics overwhelms science in the Covid-19 pandemic: Evidence from the whole coverage of the Italian quality newspapers. *PLoS ONE*, 16(5), e0252034.
- Crum, B. (2023). Party system hospitality, internal strife and radicalization: The evolution of the Partij voor de Vrijheid and the Forum voor Democratie in the Netherlands. In B. Crum & A. Oleart (Eds.), *Populist parties and democratic resilience: A cross-national analysis of populist parties' impact on democratic pluralism in Europe* (pp. 120-137). London: Routledge.
- Crum, B., & Oleart, A. (Eds.). (2023). *Populist parties and democratic resilience: A cross-national analysis of populist parties' impact on democratic pluralism in Europe*. London: Routledge.
- de Jonge, L. (2021). Is the (mass) party really over? The case of the Dutch Forum for Democracy. *Politics and Governance*, 9(4), 286-295.
- de Lange, S. (2023). The Netherlands: Divergent paths for the populist radical right. In N. Ringe & L. Rennó (Eds.), *Populists and the pandemic* (pp. 262-272). London: Routledge.

- Deegan-Krause, K., & Enyedi, Z. (2010). Agency and the structure of party competition: Alignment, stability and the role of political elites. *West European Politics*, 33(3), 686-710.
- della Porta, D. (2024). *Regressive movements in times of emergency: The protests against anti-contagion measures and vaccination during the Covid-19 pandemic*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- della Porta, D., & Caiani, M. (2007). Europeanization from below? Social movements and Europe. *Mobilization: An International Quarterly*, 12(1), 1-20.
- della Porta, D., & Lavizzari, A. (2024). Framing health and care: Legacies and innovation during the pandemic. *Social Movement Studies*, 23(6), 738-755.
- Engler, S., Brunner, P., Loviat, R., Abou-Chadi, T., Leemann, L., Glaser, A., & Kübler, D. (2021). Democracy in times of the pandemic: Explaining the variation of COVID-19 policies across European democracies. *West European Politics*, 44(5-6), 1077-1102.
- Evans, G., & Tilley, J. (2012). How parties shape class politics: Explaining the decline of the class basis of party support. *British Journal of Political Science*, 42(1), 137-161.
- Ferrera, M., Kriesi, H., & Schelkle, W. (2023). Maintaining the EU's compound polity during the long crisis decade. *Journal of European Public Policy* (online first).
- Fillieule, O., & Dafflon, A. (2013). Yellow vests movement in France. In D. A. Snow, D. della Porta, D. McAdam, & B. Klandermans (Eds.), *The Wiley-Blackwell encyclopedia of social and political movements* (pp. 1-6). Wiley.
- Fominaya, C. F. (2024). Mobilizing during the Covid-19 pandemic: From democratic innovation to the political weaponization of disinformation. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 68(6), 829-852.
- Ford, R., & Jennings, W. (2020). The changing cleavage politics of Western Europe. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 23, 295-314.
- Grande, E. (2023). Civil society, cleavage structures, and democracy in Germany. *German Politics*, 32(3), 420-439.
- Grande, E., Hutter, S., Hunger, S., & Kanol, E. (2021). Alles covidioten? Politische potenziale des corona-protests in Deutschland. *WZB Discussion Paper*, No. ZZ 2021-601.
- Hale, T., Angrist, N., Goldszmidt, R., Kira, B., Petherick, A., Phillips, T., et al. (2021).

A global panel database of pandemic policies (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker). *Nature Human Behaviour*, 5(4), 529-538.

Häusermann, S., & Kriesi, H. (2015). What do voters want? Dimensions and configurations in individual-level preferences and party choice. In P. Beramendi, S. Häusermann, H. Kitschelt, & H. Kriesi (Eds.), *The politics of advanced capitalism* (pp. 202-230). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Hellmeier, S. (2023). From masks to mismanagement: A global assessment of the rise and fall of pandemic-related protests. *Research & Politics*, 10(3), 1-9.

Hooghe, L., & Marks, G. (2018). Cleavage theory meets Europe's crises: Lipset, Rokkan, and the transnational cleavage. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 25(1), 109-135.

Hunger, S., Hutter, S., & Kanol, E. (2023). The mobilisation potential of anti-containment protests in Germany. *West European Politics*, 46(4), 812-840.

Hunt, K. (2022). Exploiting a crisis: Abortion activism and the COVID-19 pandemic. *Perspectives on Politics*, 20(2), 396-411.

Hutter, S., & Kriesi, H. (2019). Politicizing Europe in times of crisis. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(7), 996-1017.

Ignazi, P. (1992). The silent counter-revolution. Hypotheses on the emergence of extreme right-wing parties in Europe. *European Journal of Political Research*, 22(1), 3-34.

Inglehart, R., & Norris, P. (2019). *Cultural backlash: Trump, Brexit, and authoritarian populism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Jennings, W., Stoker, G., Valgarðsson, V., Devine, D., & Gaskell, J. (2021). How trust, mistrust and distrust shape the governance of the Covid-19 crisis. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 28(8), 1174-1196.

Jørgensen, F., Bor, A., Rasmussen, M. S., Lindholt, M. F., & Petersen, M. B. (2022). Pandemic fatigue fueled political discontent during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(48), e2201266119.

Kitschelt, H. (1994). *The transformation of European social democracy*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Kitschelt, H. (1995). *The radical right in Western Europe: A comparative analysis*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.

Kriesi, H., Grande, E., Lachat, R., Dolezal, M., Bornschier, S., & Frey, T. (2008). *West REGROUP Policy Paper No. 5*

European politics in the age of globalization. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Kriesi, H., & Oana, I. E. (2023). Protest in unlikely times: Dynamics of collective mobilization in Europe during the COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 30(4), 740-765.

Kritzinger, S., Foucault, M., Lachat, R., Partheymüller, J., Plescia, C., & Brouard, S. (2021). 'Rally round the flag': The COVID-19 crisis and trust in the national government. *West European Politics*, 44(5-6), 1205-1231.

Lindekilde, L. (2014). Discourse and frame analysis. In D. della Porta (Ed.), *Methodological practices in social movement research* (pp. 195-227). Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Lipiński, A. (2021). Poland: 'If we don't elect the president, the country will plunge into chaos.' In G. Bobba & N. Hubé (Eds.), *Populism and the politicization of the COVID-19 crisis in Europe* (pp. 115-129). Springer International Publishing.

Lipset, S. M., & Rokkan, S. (1967). *Party systems and voter alignments: Cross-national perspectives*. Toronto: The Free Press.

Louwerse, T., Sieberer, U., Tuttnauer, O., & Andeweg, R. B. (2021). Opposition in times of crisis: COVID-19 in parliamentary debates. *West European Politics*, 44(5-6), 1025-1051.

Malamidis, H. (2020). *Social movements and solidarity structures in crisis-ridden Greece*. Amsterdam: Amsterdam University Press.

Marks, G., Attewell, D., Rovny, J., & Hooghe, L. (2021). Cleavage theory. In M. Ridder-vold, J. Trondal, & A. Newsome (Eds.), *The Palgrave handbook of EU crises*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Moutselos, M. (2025). Geographic Variation in COVID-19 Protests in the EU-27: Actors, Grievances, and Protest Frames During a Public Health Crisis. *REGROUP Research Paper 16*.

Moffitt, B. (2015). How to perform crisis: A model for understanding the key role of crisis in contemporary populism. *Government and Opposition*, 50(2), 189-217.

Mudde, C., & Rovira Kaltwasser, C. (2018). Studying populism in comparative perspective: Reflections on the contemporary and future research agenda. *Comparative Political Studies*, 51(13), 1667-1693.

- Müller, T., Schulten, T., & Dražokoupil, J. (2022). Job retention schemes in Europe during the COVID-19 pandemic: Different shapes and sizes and the role of collective bargaining. *Transfer: European Review of Labour and Research*, 28(2), 247-265.
- Neumayer, E., Pfaff, K. G., & Plümpert, T. (2024). Protest against Covid-19 containment policies in European countries. *Journal of Peace Research*, 61(3), 398-412.
- Norris, P., & Inglehart, R. (2019). *Cultural backlash: Trump, Brexit, and authoritarian populism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Oana, I. E., Pellegata, A., & Wang, C. (2021). A cure worse than the disease? Exploring the health-economy trade-off during Covid-19. *West European Politics*, 44(5-6), 1232-1257.
- Plümpert, T., Neumayer, E., & Pfaff, K. G. (2021). The strategy of protest against Covid-19 containment policies in Germany. *Social Science Quarterly*, 102(5), 2236-2250.
- Pressman, J., & Choi-Fitzpatrick, A. (2021). Covid19 and protest repertoires in the United States: An initial description of limited change. *Social Movement Studies*, 20(6), 766-773.
- Rak, J. (2021). Framing enemies by the state television: Delegitimization of anti-government protest participants during the first wave of the pandemic in Poland. *Journal of Contemporary Central Eastern Europe*, 29, 157-175.
- Rensmann, L. (2017). The noisy counter-revolution: Understanding the cultural conditions and dynamics of populist politics in Europe in the digital age. *Politics and Governance*, 5(4), 123-135.
- Rensmann, L. (2018). Radical right-wing populists in parliament: Examining the Alternative for Germany in European context. *German Politics and Society*, 36(3), 43-71.
- Rensmann, L., & de Zee, T. (2022). The pandemic factor: The COVID-19 crisis in the Alternative for Germany's 2021 federal election campaign. *German Politics & Society*, 40(4), 69-103.
- Rensmann, L., de Lange, S., & Couperus, S. (2017). Editorial to the issue on populism and the remaking of (il)liberal democracy in Europe. *Politics and Governance*, 5(4), 106-111.
- Ringe, N., & Rennó, L. (2023). *Populists and the pandemic: How populists around the world responded to Covid-19*. London: Routledge.

- Rohlinger, D. A., & Meyer, D. S. (2024). Protest during a pandemic: How Covid-19 affected social movements in the United States. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 68(6), 810-828.
- Rovira Kaltwasser, C., & Taggart, P. (2022). The populist radical right and the pandemic. *Government and Opposition*, 1-21.
- Rovny, J., Bakker, R., Hooghe, L., Jolly, S., Marks, G., Polk, J., Steenbergen, M., & Vachudova, M. A. (2022). Contesting Covid: The ideological bases of partisan responses to the Covid-19 pandemic. *European Journal of Political Research*, 61(4), 1155-1164.
- Salvati, E. (2021). Crisis and intergovernmental retrenchment in the European Union? Framing the EU's answer to the Covid-19 pandemic. *Chinese Political Science Review*, 6, 1-19.
- Schraff, D. (2021). Political trust during the Covid-19 pandemic: Rally around the flag or lockdown effects? *European Journal of Political Research*, 60(4), 1007-1017.
- Seabrooke, L., & Tsingou, E. (2019). Crises in time: Fast- and slow-burning crises in the European Union. In K. H. Goetz (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of time and politics*. Oxford Academic.
- Slothuus, R., & Bisgaard, M. (2021). Party over pocketbook? How party cues influence opinion when citizens have a stake in policy. *American Political Science Review*, 115(3), 1090-1096.
- Snow, D. A., Rochford Jr, E. B., Worden, S. K., & Benford, R. D. (1986). Frame alignment processes, micromobilization, and movement participation. *American Sociological Review*, 51(4), 464-481.
- Stanley, B., & Czeńnik, M. (2019). Populism in Poland. In D. Stockemer (Ed.), *Populism around the world: A comparative perspective* (pp. 67-87). Springer International Publishing.
- Styczyńska, N., & Zubek, M. (2023). Poland: The “Cardboard State” Versus the Virus. In K. Lynggaard, M. D. Jensen, & M. Kluth (Eds.), *Governments' Responses to the Covid-19 Pandemic in Europe: Navigating the Perfect Storm* (pp. 111-121). Springer International Publishing.
- Thomas, A., Dörflinger, N., Yon, K., & Pletschette, M. (2024). Covid-19 and health and safety at work: Trade union dilemmas in Germany, France and Luxembourg (March 2020-December 2021). *Economic and Industrial Democracy*, 45(1), 116-137.

- Truchlewski, Z., Schelkle, W., & Ganderson, J. (2021). Buying time for democracies? European Union emergency politics in the time of Covid-19. *West European Politics*, 44(5-6), 1353-1375.
- Turska-Kawa, A., Csanyi, P., & Kucharčík, R. (2022). From the ‘rally ‘round the flag’ effect to a social crisis of confidence: Poland and Slovakia in the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Comparative Politics*, 15(1), 20-38.
- van der Meer, T., Steenvoorden, E., & Ouattara, E. (2023). Fear and the COVID-19 rally round the flag: A panel study on political trust. *West European Politics* (online first).
- Vashchanka, V. (2020). Political manoeuvres and legal conundrums amid the COVID-19 pandemic: The 2020 presidential election in Poland. International IDEA.
- Volk, S. (2023). Resisting ‘leftist dictatorship’? Memory politics and collective action framing in populist far-right street protest. *European Politics and Society*, 24(5), 535-551.
- Volk, S., & Weisskircher, M. (2024). Defending democracy against the ‘corona dictatorship’? Far-right PEGIDA during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Social Movement Studies*, 23(6), 719-737.
- Volk, S., de Jonge, L., & Rensmann, L. (2023). Populism and the pandemic: The politicization of COVID-19 and cleavage agency among populist radical right parties. *REGROUP Research Paper 7*.
- Volpi, E., Cicchi, L., & Widmann, T. (2022). “Pandemic frames: How is the European Union narrated by Italian (populist) parties during Covid-19’s first wave in Italy”, in “Populism on contemporary Italian politics: actors and processes in time of crisis”, Calossi, E. & Imperatore, P. (eds), Pisa: Pisa University Press.
- Wondreys, J., & Mudde, C. (2022). Victims of the pandemic? European far-right parties and COVID-19. *Nationalities Papers*, 50(1), 86-103.
- Zulianello, M., & Guasti, P. (2023). The demand and supply of pandemic populism: A global overview. *Government and Opposition*, 1-20.